

THE EFFECTIVE USE OF ORAL SPEECH AS A MEANS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This thesis analyzes oral speech widely used in the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages, that allows students to get involved in verbal communication. Developing practical skills that may be needed in the future to improve professional abilities. Mastering oral speech helps to overcome problems associated with self-doubt when learning a language. The understanding of oral speech occurs as a result of the perception of speech and its comprehension.*

Keywords: *concept, verbal, socio-historical, mastering, comprehension, authentic, proficiency, phenomenon, input material.*

One of the most worldwide spoken languages today is English. Learning English opens the door to the world library of knowledge, as many scientific and literary publications are written in English.

Speaking about the difficulties of teaching a foreign language, it is impossible not to consider the concept of language. I.A. Zimnyaya offers the following definition of language: language is “a complex systemic level formation through which a person’s conceptual (verbal) thinking is formed and the development of all his higher mental functions is mediated and which is the main means of human communication” [1,2]. According to W. Humboldt, language is “the soul of a nation, it captures all of its “national” character. Being a socio-historical product, language thus also provides a link between different generations that speak this language.

Oral speech is widely used in the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages, which allows students to get involved in verbal communication. With the purposeful use of communication, there is an active process of developing those practical skills that may be needed in the future to improve professional abilities. The correct use of oral speech in the process of teaching a foreign language arouses great interest and desire among students to study it.

The goal of language learning, provides the opportunity for direct communication, mastering oral speech helps to overcome problems associated with self-doubt when learning a language; developing, mastering the structure of the

language in oral speech and improving other aspects of speech activity, i.e. students are provided with the opportunity to hear and see how, in what situations, the input words or grammatical structures are used.

In methodological terms, it is essential that listening and speaking, being in close relationship, contribute to the development of each other in the learning process. The observations of psychologists have established that the understanding of oral speech occurs as a result of the perception of speech and its comprehension. Speaking is a type of speech activity through which verbal communication is carried out.

“In order to learn to understand speech, it is necessary to speak, and by how your speech will be received, judge your understanding. Understanding is formed in the process of speaking, and speaking in the process of understanding”. According to A.A. Leontiev, inner speech and related articulation are the main mechanism of speech thinking and take place both in listening to foreign speech and authentic materials [3].

Speech activity is realized due to the complex psychophysiological mechanism of speech activity. Many researchers pay attention to the connection between the psychological content of activity and the psychophysiological mechanisms of activity.

Students observe a new phenomenon in oral speech, listen in order to understand the meaning of the material being introduced. The attention of students is directed to the content of the statement, in which new information is presented. Their task is to understand, comprehend, realize the input material.

Thus, it should be noted that in order to use oral speech effectively as the means of teaching a foreign language, attention should be paid to the implementation of the following factors: the teacher must be fluent in the language being taught and adapt his oral speech to the specific conditions of the audience, without violating the authenticity of speech; be creative when using standard learning technologies; maintain a high level of foreign language proficiency through constant language studies, by reading original literature, listening to audio materials and watching original video materials in foreign languages. In addition, the teacher must know the capabilities of each student individually for the choice of methodological techniques, as well as the use of real situations. To improve the quality of education, it is necessary to pay attention to additional visual aids that serve to facilitate the assimilation of educational material, as well as to ensure a sufficiently high level of employment.

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